

POLYSEMY IN AVIATION LANGUAGE: A COGNITIVE APPROACH**Valya Tsvetanova**

Abstract: *Aviation language is characterised by unique features that make this language specific, context-dependent, we can also say predictable. What first comes to mind when we think of aviation terminology is that it is heavily context-dependent, precise, unambiguous. Synonymy, idiomatic expressions and polysemy are avoided and if we consult an aviation dictionary, we can see that most terms have one main meaning. However, we have mentioned that language is a system that is more than words; therefore, we believe that even though aviation terminology is specific, the terms used in the aviation terminological field possess versatile nature and their technical, scientific meanings can be referred to as extensions of their prototypes. Thus, we propose the hypothesis that even though polysemy is avoided in aviation language, there are cases of polysemous terms – terms that are conceptually related and connected to a prototype. We have noted that some aviation terms, before entering the aviation domain, were part of general English. When these terms entered the specialized domain, they acquired a new meaning. A question arises as to whether these meanings are entirely unrelated to the old meanings or whether they are an extension of prototype meanings? This research will be an attempt to demonstrate that even highly technical and scientific terminology can display a versatile nature, thus confirming researchers' proposition that language is a system that represents people's ability to create multiple mental pictures for a single concept.*

Keywords: *cognitive linguistics, radial categories, polysemy, aviation terms*

ПОЛИСЕМИЯ В АВИАЦИОННИЯ ЕЗИК – КОГНИТИВЕН ПОДХОД**Валя Цветанова**

Резюме: *Авиационният език се характеризира с уникални особености, които го правят специфичен, зависим от контекста и, можем да кажем, предсказуем. Първото нещо, което ни идва на ум, когато мислим за авиационната терминология, е, че тя е силно зависима от контекста, точна и недвусмислена. Синонимията, идиоматичните изрази и полисемията се избягват и ако потърсим термин в авиационен речник, ще видим, че повечето от тях имат едно основно значение. Въпреки това, както вече споменахме, езикът е система, която е нещо повече от думи; следователно считаме, че макар терминологията в авиацията да е специфична, термините, използвани в терминологичната област на авиацията, притежават многостранен характер и техните технически и научни значения могат да бъдат разглеждани като разширения на техните прототипи. И така, предполагаме като хипотеза, че макар полисемията да се избягва в авиационния език, има случаи на полисемични термини – термини, които са концептуално съотносими и свързани с прототип. Отбелязахме, че някои авиационни термини, преди да влязат в авиационната област, са били част от общия английски език. Когато тези термини са станали част от специализираната област, те са придобили ново значение. Възниква*

въпросът дали тези значения са напълно несвързани със старите значения или са разширение на прототипните значения? Това изследване ще бъде опит да се докаже, че дори високотехническата и научната терминология може да проявява многостранен характер, потвърждавайки по този начин тезата на изследователите, че езикът е система, която отразява способността на хората да създават множество ментални образи за едно и също понятие.

Ключови думи: когнитивна лингвистика, радиални категории, полисемия, авиационни термини

1. Introduction

English became the official language of aviation in the 1950s. Aviation English represents a language, which was made to meet certain requirements such as brevity, conciseness and unambiguity. According to ICAO, Doc. 9835, the term *Aviation English* is relatively broad because the aviation terminological field includes “All of the language uses of many different professions (engineers, technicians, commercial staff, flight crews, etc.) within the aviation domain, which itself includes specializations such as aircraft construction, aircraft maintenance, aircraft operations, air traffic control, regulation, airport activities, passenger care, and flight crew operations” (ICAO, 2010, p. 3-2).

Aviation language is characterised by its specific rules which aim to simplify the language, thus creating a successful means of conveying clear and unambiguous messages. Special attention has been paid to terms and their meanings. As a rule, polysemy is not encouraged as it can cause confusion, misunderstandings which can lead to fatal consequences. Much of the research on aviation language is related to communication issues caused by aviation professionals’ inability to use English, the structural and lexical characteristics of Aviation English – Katsarska (Katsarska, 2024, 2021), Fainman (Fainman, 2018), Estival (Estival, 2016), Lopez et al. (Lopez et al., 2013). There is some interesting and fruitful research on polysemy in the aviation language done by Kulieva (Kulieva, 2019) or Anurova and Ivanova (Anurova, Ivanova, 2021). The topic of whether polysemy is a phenomenon that exists in the aviation terminological field needs further analysis; therefore, the aim of our research is to look at this phenomenon from a different perspective, namely through the lens of Cognitive linguistics.

Most terms belonging to the aviation terminological field are of Latin, Greek or French origin, e.g. *aerodynamics, aileron, altimeter, fuselage*. Other terms were first used only in everyday English and entered the aviation domain later over the years, e.g. *bank, lift, apron, stall*. A third group of terms was borrowed from nautical terminology. Terms such as *rudder, heading, yaw or roll* entered aviation terminology mostly due to the fact that aircraft and flying were considered similar to ships and sailing in terms of navigation and control. Another group of terms was borrowed from other sciences, particularly physics, meteorology, and mathematics. For example, *momentum, angle of attack, inertia, gradient, dew point*. With the advancement in technology and aviation, new concepts have entered the aviation domain, thus enriching and expanding it, which proves that even though Aviation English is

considered specialised, scientific and technical, it is a living language that is still developing. Therefore, today we can talk about *drones* or *unmanned aerial vehicles*, *supersonic* and *hypersonic flights*, *fly-by-wire*.

It is evident that aviation terminology has been influenced by various factors, each of which has contributed to the development of highly specific and context-dependent vocabulary. As previously mentioned, Aviation English avoids polysemous words because they may cause confusion and misunderstanding. Thus, one may conclude that the terms used in aviation are generally monosemous. At first glance, this proposition can be accepted without hesitation.

However, with the development of Cognitive linguistics, new approaches to language have emerged and revealed that language is more than words and meanings. Words are not only analysed by their dictionary meaning but all the knowledge a person has about the surrounding world and their experience plays a crucial role in understanding how language actually functions. Therefore, according to Cognitive linguistics, language is more than just a means of communication. Language is a reflection of how a person thinks, perceives the surrounding world, and processes information. Our experiences and thoughts are structured in cognitive models, which, according to Lakoff (Lakoff, 1987, p. 118), help us understand the world.

The idea of embodiment in Cognitive linguistics supports the proposition that language cannot be separated from the human body and physical experience. As Johnson (Johnson, 1987, p. 29) notes the recurring patterns of human movements and experiences, also known as image schemas, make people's experience meaningful. In other words, image schemas help us understand abstract ideas by providing concepts and conceptual domain with structure. According to Geeraerts (Geeraerts, 2021, p. 23), reality can be described on the basis of concepts that already exist in the language. He gives an example of the prototypical models of categorisation, where typical examples are considered core concepts, and less typical ones are in the periphery. On the other hand, how we perceive and interpret a situation influences the way we structure concepts.

It is evident that language is a dynamic system, shaped by people's encyclopedic knowledge and is constantly evolving. Since language changes over time, it can be accepted that meaning changes as well. Therefore, we propose that we cannot confine meaning to a single dictionary entry and expect that this meaning will not be influenced by experiences and thoughts.

Aviation language is characterised by unique features that make this language specific, context-dependent, we can also say predictable. What first comes to mind when we think of aviation terminology is that it is heavily context-dependent, precise, unambiguous. Synonymy, idiomatic expressions and polysemy are avoided and if we consult an aviation dictionary, we can see that most terms have one main meaning. However, we have mentioned that language is a system that is more than words; therefore, we believe that even though aviation terminology is specific, the terms used in the aviation terminological field possess versatile nature and their technical, scientific meanings can be referred to as extensions of their prototype.

Thus, we propose the hypothesis that even though polysemy is avoided in aviation language, there are cases of polysemous terms –terms that are conceptually

related and connected to a prototype. Yet, it is important to note that if our hypothesis turns out to be true, the polysemous terms do not lead to confusion, ambiguity, or miscommunication among aviation professionals.

We have noted that some aviation terms, before entering the aviation domain, were part of general English. When these terms entered the specialized domain, they acquired a new meaning. Consequently, a question arises as to whether these meanings are entirely unrelated to the old meanings or whether they are an extension of prototype meanings. In other words, are these terms examples of homonymy or polysemy?

To find out the answer to this question, we will discuss aviation terms through the lens of Cognitive linguistics, more precisely we will use Lakoff's approach to Radial categories. This research will be an attempt to demonstrate that even highly technical and scientific terminology can display a versatile nature, thus confirming researchers' proposition that language is a system that represents people's ability to create multiple mental pictures for a single concept.

1.1. Polysemy and Homonymy

Polysemy is a linguistic phenomenon that has been researched over the years and is still open to discussion among linguists. Polysemy is almost always associated with general language usage and there are efforts to minimise its use in more specific, scientific and technical discourse. The assumption that multiple meanings can lead to ambiguity and misunderstanding has led to discussions about whether polysemy is acceptable in scientific discourse.

It has always been difficult to distinguish polysemy from homonymy. Homonymy studies words with different and unrelated meanings and they are referred to as separate lexical entities.

Nerlich and Clarke (Nerlich, Clarke, 2003, pp. 4-5) point out that with the emergence of cognitive linguistics and the establishment of theories of how people categorise on the basis of prototypes and resemblance, polysemy has been seen as "a category in which the senses of the word (i.e. the members of the category) are related to each other by means of general cognitive principles such as metaphor, metonymy, generalization, specialization, and image-schema transformations". They also note that cognitive linguists focus on polysemy by studying metaphor, metonymy, prototypes, conceptual blending, and semantic frames. Therefore, polysemy is not referred to as a problem but as an essential feature of language, language use, and cognition.

According to Nerlich and Clarke (Nerlich, Clarke, 2003, p. 7), polysemy can be understood if it is studied from linguistic, cognitive, and cultural perspectives. They also point out that research in cognitive linguistics has shown that polysemy can be explained through conceptual and cultural metaphors. The meanings of multiple words do not appear at random, but they follow patterns related to human cognition and encyclopedic knowledge; therefore, Nerlich and Clarke (ibid.) note that understanding the structures of metaphor and metonymy leads to understanding why polysemy appears and how it is structured. They also add that language is not seen as

a system of fixed meanings but enables people to create new meanings by cognitive processes that construct new meanings. Consequently, linguistic expressions do not have pre-determined meanings, but they are prompts that help people construct meaning using knowledge and experience. Polysemy is a dynamic process which is context-dependent and is influenced by cognitive processing in language use.

1.2. Radial Categories

Polysemy is a linguistic phenomenon in which a single word has multiple meanings that are related. Referring to Lakoff's conception of categorisation (Lakoff, 1987), Brugman and Lakoff (Brugman, Lakoff, 1988) note that categories have internal structure, in which some members are seen as better examples than others. Lakoff (Lakoff, 1987, p. 91) introduces the idea of radial categories which have a central member and a network of links to other members. On this theoretical basis, Brugman and Lakoff (ibid.) note that a polysemous word is a radial category with a more central meaning and other meanings linked to it. They also point out that this structure is not randomly formed but it is a common category structure "that occurs in domains other than the lexicon." Lakoff (Lakoff, 1987, p. 91) notes that "The central model determines the possibilities for extensions, together with the possible relations between the central model and the extension models". Therefore, it is accepted that the links between members are not random, and the theory of radial categories explains possible link types. For polysemy, these types of links are the relations that link multiple meanings of a single word. These links may have shared information, they may connect general and specific concepts, or they may be metaphorical. According to Lakoff (Lakoff, 1987a, p. 379), the connections between the central meaning and its extensions differ from each other; therefore, these connections cannot be explained by a single explanation or definition. Also, these extensions are neither random nor predictable and their occurrence is always motivated by linguistic and extralinguistic features. To understand how these meanings are linked to the core sense, "all the kinds of cognitive models...: propositional, metaphorical, metonymic, and image-schematic" can be applied.

Radial categories support the idea that language is built on cognitive models, which depend on people's perspectives and how they interpret the situation. Lakoff's famous example shows how the concept of 'mother' can be the center of a radial category with its extensions influenced by how a person views it – "the female, who gives birth; the female, who nurtures and raises a child; or the wife of the father" (Lakoff, 1987, p. 74).

Lewandowska-Tomaszczyk (Lewandowska-Tomaszczyk, 2012, p. 29) adds that meanings can extend and they can occur in another domain. When these meanings occur in more than one domain and they are based on a single ICM, then they create chains of related meanings, i.e. "Extended beyond one domain, single-ICM polysemies can form chains of senses, all motivated by other related senses as well as by principles of linking meaning components in language". She concludes that polysemy is a kind of categorisation because the meanings of a word form a chain of related ideas, which are shaped by a person's perspectives. These meanings are built around a core, and they display some commonalities rather than differences. It is worth noting that as language is dynamic and evolving, so is categorisation.

2. Research and discussion

For the purpose of the following research, we will study the terms that denote the four forces of flight, namely weight, lift, drag and thrust. They are usually used both in general and scientific language. These terms are central concepts in the aviation terminological system, more precisely in aerodynamics. Aerodynamic terminology is highly specialised, most of the terms belong to other terminological fields, such as physics, mathematics, and meteorology. These terms denote specific, complex scientific phenomena that only aviation professionals can understand.

Using Lakoff's Radial Category, we will demonstrate that even specific, scientific, emotionless language can exhibit cases of polysemous terminology. The terms, which we will research, were first part of the general language lexicon and, with the advancement in aviation, they entered the field acquiring a new meaning. Our proposition is that these new meanings are actually extensions from a core (prototypical) meaning and each of these meanings is related in some way to both the core sense and the other extensions in the domain.

2.1. LIFT

Etymologically, the meaning of the noun originates from the mid-14th century, meaning '*a man's load, as much as a man can carry*' and in the 15th century, it acquired the meaning of '*act or action of lifting*'. It was 1902 when the noun *lift* was first used in aviation, meaning '*upward force of an aircraft*'¹. Following Lakoff's ideas of radial categories, we can propose that the central meaning of the noun *lift* is '*the act or action of lifting*'.

To demonstrate how other meanings are extended from the central one, we will use the following sentences:

(1) General language:

- *My selection for the team has given me a tremendous lift.*
- *They **took the lift** to the fourth floor.*
- *It's good to watch it from time to time to **give myself a lift**.*
(Times, Sunday Times, 2017)
- *He had a car and often **gave me a lift home**².*

(2) Specialised discourse:

- *To maintain this basic flight situation, **the lift equals the weight**, and the thrust equals the drag (Talay, 1975, p. 24).*
- *In level flight, **a lift force equal to the weight** must be produced.*
- *The pilot can achieve **maximum lift** by pulling hard back on the controls (Crocker, 2007, p. 136).*

As mentioned above, the links that extend from the core meaning involve relations that are beyond lexical relations. Lakoff (Lakoff, 1987, p. 109) notes that meaning extensions must be motivated – new meanings cannot be arbitrary.

¹ <https://www.etymonline.com/search?q=lift>.

² <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/sentences/english/lift>.

Consequently, categorization in language is systematic. The examples of the noun *lift* show that it has a core meaning and the meanings that extend from it are related conceptually (upwards/forwards movement), e.g. *took a lift*, *the lift equals the weight*, and *achieved maximum lift*.

The noun *lift* is also motivated metaphorically, e.g. *a tremendous lift or give myself a lift*, meaning positive emotions (happiness, excitement).

Gave me a lift is extended from the core one with the meaning 'act of helping' (originated from 1630s)³.

The core meaning is preserved in aviation discourse and is technically described as it is context dependent. We can suggest that aviation terms follow structured patterns in language and the meanings they acquire are extended from the central meaning of the category, and not developed randomly but they are motivated, instead.

While researching the noun *lift*, we noticed that among the meanings discussed above, *lift (n)* also means *an act of stealing: theft*⁴. These two meanings seem quite distant and unrelated. Therefore, a question has arisen; namely, is this meaning an extension of the central meaning of lift, which we discussed above, or can we propose that it is a case of homonymy (the meanings of a single word are not related)? To find the answer to this question, we used the online etymology dictionary – <https://www.etymonline.com/>. We could not find any information about how the meaning in question developed. However, when we looked up the verb *to lift*, we found that the meaning 'steal, take up dishonestly' appeared in the 1520s. Therefore, we can propose that this meaning is actually an extension from the verb *to lift*, which has the meaning of 'to take hold of and raise something in order to remove, carry, or move it to a different position'⁵. Conceptually, these meanings can be related as when a person steals something, they usually raise it to remove or carry it. Consequently, we can propose that it is a case of polysemy rather than of homonymy.

Thus, we can conclude that *lift* is a polysemous term and is an extension from the core sense of *the act of action of lifting*. Figure 1 represents the radial category of *Lift*, showing the extensions from the central meaning.

³ <https://www.etymonline.com/search?q=lift>.

⁴ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/lift>.

⁵ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/lift>.

Fig. 1. Radial category of *Lift*

2.2. WEIGHT

According to the *Dictionary of Aviation*, the term *weight* means *the force with which a body is drawn towards the centre of the Earth* (Crocker, 2007, p. 250). To find out whether this meaning is an extension of a prototype, we will examine the word from a diachronic perspective.

Weight comes from Old English *wiht*, *gewiht* meaning *weighing, downward force of a body, physical property of heaviness*⁶. It is evident that the meaning has not undergone a change over time. Therefore, we suggest that the meaning of the aerodynamic term *weight* and the core meaning of the word *weight* is an example of systematic polysemy. It means that the aerodynamic meaning is not conceptually motivated, but it is an extension of the core sense which is specific for a given context.

Thus, we can provide the following examples:

(3) *The boat sank under the **weight** of the cargo*⁷.

(4) ***Weight** is a force that is always directed toward the center of the earth*⁸.

In the 14th century, the word *weight* acquired the figurative meaning of *burden*, which, we propose, was conceptually motivated by people's experiences as it carries the sense of something heavy and difficult to carry or endure. We could not find examples of *weight* used figuratively in aviation texts, which confirms that specialised language is specific, and that this term is used with its primary meaning in a scientific context.

⁶ <https://www.etymonline.com/search?q=weight>.

⁷ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/sentences/weight>.

⁸ <https://www1.grc.nasa.gov/beginners-guide-to-aeronautics/four-forces-on-an-airplane/>.

In contrast, we can find examples of the figurative meaning in general English, such as:

- (5) *The **weight of expectation** was getting to them.*
(6) *Companies found themselves collapsing under the **weight of debts***⁹.

By the 1520s, the word *weight* acquired a new meaning of *importance*. Jostmann et al. (Jostmann et al., 2009, p. 1169) did research which showed that people interpret the concept of importance through their body experience or the idea that abstract thinking is related to physical experience.

“... the abstract concept of importance is grounded in bodily experiences of weight. ... In line with an embodied perspective on cognition, these findings suggest that, much as weight makes people invest more physical effort in dealing with concrete objects, it also makes people invest more cognitive effort in dealing with abstract issues” (Jostmann et al., 2009, p. 1169).

Therefore, we can conclude that this sense of weight is based on the primary metaphor *Importance is weight*, or we know it because we have learnt it through our experience. Yu et al. (Yu et al., 2017, p. 231) suggest that the primary metaphor *Importance is weight* is “derived from the OBJECT image schema, abstracted from our embodied, sensorimotor experience, especially our visual and tactile perception, in dealing with physical objects in everyday life”.

Thus, we can find sentences such as:

- (7) *The Association's reports **carry weight** because it stands for independence and integrity.*
(8) *The guidelines **give greater weight to economic potential***¹⁰.

It is evident that the concept *weight* exhibits polysemy, which is expressed in different ways. We provided examples demonstrating that the central meaning can be preserved and mapped onto another domain (systematic polysemy). We also showed that *weight* can be polysemous, having extensions based on conceptual and primary metaphors. This once again shows that language and cognition are intertwined and cannot be separated.

⁹ <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/sentences/english/weight>.

¹⁰ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/weight>.

Fig. 2. Radial category of *Weight*

2.3. TRUST

Another force that acts on aircraft is the *thrust*. The term is defined as *a force produced by a propeller, jet or rocket* (Crocker, 2007, p. 233). The noun *thrust* originates from the 1510s and has the meaning of an *act of pressing*. It comes from the verb *thrust* (push, jostle, shove; stab with a weapon). The meaning of *propulsive force* dates back to 1708¹¹. Nowadays, the word *thrust* has retained its meaning, and we can identify senses such as *1) a forward or upward push or 2) a movement (as by a group of people) in a specified direction*¹². Therefore, we accept that the core meaning is *the act of pressing, pushing in a specialised direction*. We propose that ‘*in a specialised direction*’ should be included in the central meaning because we believe that the sense of the word is composed of two components: *force (push, jostle, stab-they all require force)* and *direction (the force is directed towards something or someone)*. Therefore, we can conclude that *thrust* is an example of embodiment, an experience related to the outer world. This can be mapped onto the aerodynamic meaning, as the force is generated by an engine or propeller, and it makes the aircraft move in a particular direction. It proves that this meaning is not random, but it is related to the idea that *a force causes motion along a particular path*.

According to the online dictionary <https://www.etymonline.com/>, *thrust* acquired a figurative meaning of ‘*principal theme, aim, point, purpose*’ in 1968. When we look up the Merriam-Webster online English dictionary (<https://www.merriam-webster.com/>), the following meanings are listed:

¹¹ <https://www.etymonline.com/search?q=thrust>.

¹² <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/thrust>.

- 1) salient or essential element or meaning: the *thrust* of the argument;
- 2) principal concern or objective: the plan's major *thrust* is testing – Ryan Lizza¹³.

A question arises as to whether these two meanings are actually extensions from the prototype we defined above, or they can be considered as cases of homonymy.

The thrust of argument refers to the main point of an argument which aligns with the figurative meaning given above. Lakoff and Johnson discuss the conceptual metaphor *ARGUMENT IS WAR*, pointing out that

“We don't just talk about arguments in terms of war. We can actually win or lose arguments. We see the person we are arguing with as an opponent. We attack his positions and we defend our own. We gain and lose ground. We plan and use strategies. If we find a position indefensible, we can abandon it and take a new line of attack. Many of the things we do in arguing are partially structured by the concept of war. Though there is no physical battle, there is a verbal battle, and the structure of an argument—attack, defense, counterattack, etc.—reflects this. It is in this sense that the ARGUMENT IS WAR metaphor is one that we live by in this culture; it structures the actions we perform in arguing” (Lakoff, Johnson, 1987, p. 5).

Therefore, we suggest that *thrust of argument* is a conceptual metaphor, which is an extension from the central meaning, namely: *act of pressing, pushing in a specialised direction*. When we want to defend our main point we use *force, power* (here used metaphorically) to convince (*motion*) someone of our point of view, someone who is standing opposite us (*direction*). Thus, we can have sentences, such as:

(9) *The thrust of his argument* was that change was needed¹⁴.

(10) The main thrust of her argument was that women are compromised by the demands of childcare¹⁵.

Meaning 2) *principal concern or objective* also aligns with the figurative sense of *principal theme, aim, point, purpose*. We suggest that it can be referred to as an extension from the central meaning because we view it as a conceptual metaphor which includes *force-motion-direction*. It is closely related to the explanation above. When we have a goal (aim) we use *force* to make it the central idea of something; we do our best to achieve it by certain actions (*motion*), and there is a certain direction towards its achievement.

We conclude that all the above senses of the prototype meaning are not cases of homonymy but of polysemy.

¹³ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/thrust>.

¹⁴ https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/thrust_2.

¹⁵ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/thrust>.

Fig. 3. Radial category of *Thrust*

2.4. DRAG

Etymologically, the word *drag* originates from c. 1300, *drage*, "dragnet," perhaps from a Scandinavian source (compare Old Norse *dragma* "a load," Swedish *dragg* "grapnel") or from Old English *dræge* "dragnet," related to *dragan* "to draw". From 1708 as "anything attached to a moving body that retards its progress". As the name of a device for retarding or stopping the rotation of wheels, 1795. The sense of "annoying, boring person or thing" is 1813, perhaps from the mechanical senses or the notion of something that must be dragged as an impediment¹⁶. These senses are still preserved, and we can define *drag* (*n*) as:

- i) something used to drag with;*
- ii) something that is dragged, pulled, or drawn along or over a surface;*
- iii) something which slows or impedes motion, action, or advancement¹⁷.*

Therefore, we identify the core meaning as *the act of drawing something and experiencing resistance or impediment*. Thus, we can find the following sentences:

(11) *The satellite acts as a drag on the shuttle.*

(12) *Spending cuts will put a drag on growth¹⁸.*

The *act of drawing* implies in itself the idea of something which requires effort, something which a person finds difficult to deal with. Therefore, we suggest that the extension with the sense of something boring that seems to last for a long time or something which is not appealing is a conceptual metaphor. For example,

(13) *A dry sandwich is a drag to eat.*

¹⁶ <https://www.etymonline.com/search?q=drag>.

¹⁷ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/drag>.

¹⁸ <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/drag>.

To explain this sense, we will turn to our perceptions, feelings and the idea of embodiment. Eating a dry sandwich is related to the sense of something unpleasant, requires effort, and a person feels resistance to it.

In aviation language, *drag* is defined as **the resistance of the air created by moving the aircraft through the air** (Crocker, 2007, p. 77). *Drag is the friction from fluids like air and water*¹⁹. Using the definition, we can say that there is movement and something which impedes it (the air). In addition, when we draw something, there is always some kind of friction. Therefore, we believe that the senses are related to each other. The aerodynamic term is an extension from the core meaning, which means that it is an example of polysemy.

(14) *To reduce the effect of drag on an aircraft by the fixed undercarriage a retractable type was introduced* (Crocker, 2007, p. 77).

The idea of drawing (friction), effort and resistance can be spotted in the following sentence:

(15) *(snooker) "Played it with drag as well, Dennis. I mean absolutely beautifully played, that was: drag on the cue ball so once it's made contact with the object ball there's hardly any life left on it. ..."* – John Parrott²⁰.

(15) is an example of how *drag* can be used metaphorically, mapping the core meaning onto another domain, thus creating a polysemous extension.

*Drag shot is a finesse stroke (usually over a long distance, often the full length of the table) where just enough backspin is applied to the cueball so that it will expire moments before contact with the object ball and finally roll with neither backspin or topspin at a slow pace*²¹.

In this case, *drag* refers to a specific stroke where the ball is slowed down because of friction. Consequently, it is an example of friction (draw) and resistance, and it can be classified as a polysemous extension that belongs to the Sports domain.

One of the definitions of *drag* is *the costumes worn by drag performers; costume; a costume used to impersonate a person or kind of person*²².

(16) *a giant teddy bear from which she popped to cavort with a dance troupe in fuzzy bear drag*²³.

The meaning is obviously quite distant from the others discussed above; therefore, we decided to examine whether it is a case of homonymy, or it can be related to the core meaning *the act of drawing something and experiencing resistance or impediment*.

Studying the meaning from a diachronic point of view, it became clear that the meaning originates from a slang word related to theater performances. We also relate it to the sense *women's clothing worn by a man ...from the sensation of long*

¹⁹ <https://physics.info/drag/>.

²⁰ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/drag>.

²¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cue_sports_techniques#:~:text=The%20drag%20shot%20is%20a,topspin%20at%20a%20slow%20pace.

²² <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/drag>.

²³ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/drag>.

*skirts trailing on the floor*²⁴. We propose that *drag* is a case of polysemy rather than homonymy because it can be related to the central meaning.

In the past only men were allowed to act on stage and they used to dress up as women. The dresses were long and heavy, and it was difficult to walk on the stage dressed as a woman. Because of the length, dresses dragged on the stage but also impeded the actors' movement. As mentioned above, Cognitive linguistics relies not only on cognition but also on encyclopedic knowledge and culture. Therefore, we believe that in this case *drag* exhibits polysemy.

Figure 4 illustrates the radial category of DRAG, showing the extensions of the core meaning and their usage in various contexts.

Fig. 4. Radial category of *Drag*

Conclusion

The research confirms that meaning is not limited to dictionary definitions but is also related to our experiences, knowledge and context (Evans, Green, 2006, p. 206). By studying these four essential aerodynamic terms (lift, weight, thrust and drag), we were able to demonstrate that meaning is more than a dictionary definition. Using various examples, it became evident that sometimes polysemy is not so obvious and to be able to find such cases, a person has to look at it from a different perspective, using the knowledge of the surrounding world. This is because language is not static and fixed, but it is constantly evolving as is the world around us. It is evident that meaning is a result from both linguistic and cognitive processes, influenced by people's knowledge about the world and, last but not least, the culture and customs shared among people belonging to a particular community or society. We

²⁴ <https://www.etymonline.com/search?q=drag>.

demonstrated how various senses developed through conceptual mapping leading to a metaphorical extension. Our research also showed that there are cases when the technical meaning is a result of a specialised extension rather than conceptual metaphor, which proves that meaning can also be motivated by context.

LIFT has preserved its meaning of *raising* even in meanings that seem distant and unrelated to the core sense. Thus, phrases such as *give someone a tremendous lift*, *give someone a lift home* and *lift equals weigh* are referred to as extensions from the same core meaning. Our study also showed that meaning can be preserved even in different domains. The meaning of the aerodynamic term WEIGHT has not changed when it entered the aviation terminological field, which is an example of systematic polysemy. Yet, we demonstrated that the aerodynamic meaning is still related to the other extensions from the core sense, which proves its polysemous nature. The third term, which we discussed – THRUST, also showed that its meaning can be constructed by the schema *force-motion-direction* and by the use of metaphors, such as ARGUMENT IS WAR. Moreover, our research showed that radial extensions can be related to the central sense even through the use of a person's knowledge about the customs and traditions of the past, thus relating DRAG to clothes and acting.

We can conclude that our research has shown that there are cases of polysemous terms, even in a highly specialised and technical field. However, it is worth noting that these polysemous technical extensions do not lead to misunderstanding, ambiguity and confusion, which is the primary aim of aviation language.

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